

Book Roundtable

How Islam Rules in Iran

by Mehran Kamrava

This roundtable features a single work, *How Islam Rules in Iran*, a recent and timely book that examines the evolution of Islam as a ruling framework in the post-revolutionary Iran. The author, Mehran Kamrava, undertakes an ambitious task of examining the institutional structure of the clerical establishment before addressing the question of Iranian Shia jurisprudence. Here, Dr. Kamrava engages in various interpretations and debates concerning *fiqh* and *Velayat-e Faqih*, religious reformism, *ijtihad* and Islamic democracy and how specific traditional interpretation of the concepts have shaped the country while the reformist interpretations were suppressed in the meantime. Kamrava also engages in detailed analyses of the reformist interpretations by Hasan Yousefi Eshkevari, Mohsen Kadivar and Mohammad Mojtahed Shabestari. In doing so, Kamrava addresses the shortcomings of the hermeneutics movement and why the movement was unable to reform the republic from within.

The roundtable features reviews of the book by three scholars, namely Paola Rivetti, Eric Lob and Norma Claire Moruzzi. Each reviewer provides thoughtful comments and criticism of the book. As we did in our past book review roundtables, we shared the reviews with the author to respond. We are grateful to all three reviewers and Dr. Kamrava for their thought-provoking exchanges.

How Islam Rules in Iran came out at a critical time when the war in Gaza is expanding to other regional countries and the tension between Israel and Iran is escalating. Iran also held presidential elections in 2014 and elected Masoud Pezeshkian as the new president. We hope that our readers find *How Islam Rules in Iran* and its three reviews useful to understand the institutional structure of the clerical establishment as well as some internal dynamics in Iran.

- Gamze Çavdar

Paola Rivetti, Dublin City University

Paola Rivetti is associate professor of politics and IR at Dublin City University. She is associate editor at the Journal of Iranian Studies and Partecipazione e conflitto. She is a member of the council of the British Society for Middle Eastern Studies.

With this book, *How Islam Rules Iran*, Kamrava positions himself as a fundamental scholar of contemporary Iranian political thought, having published important books in the past and continuing to refine his systemic analysis of Iranian intellectuality. In fact, one of the most relevant contributions of this book is its approach to Iranian intellectuals as a social category embedded in material conditions and power relations, which influence – if not determine – their epistemological approach to religious exegesis and politics. Kamrava shows how to overcome a scholarship interested in progressive thinkers only by treating them as organic intellectuals, who build up on past genealogical lines of intellectuality and who are divided in generations (see chapters 5-7); and by locating them in larger landscapes of intellectual production where conservative thinkers, too, operate. In this sense, Kamrava successfully shows that there is a strong intellectual dimension to institutions in Iran, and that the Islamic Republic is not simply “authoritarian”, as those authoritarian regime structures are the result of intellectual engagements and decades-long debates. A good example of this is chapter 8: a rare example of rigorous analysis dedicated to Ali Khamenei’s intellectual production and its implications for the government and governance system of Iran. More of this kind of work is needed for scholars and social scien-

tists to deepen their understanding of Iranian politics and state institutions at large.

Reading Kamrava’s book at the time of the second anniversary of the outbreak of the Woman Life Freedom uprising also prompts the question of how social movements and intellectual production interact. While reading the book, I could not stop asking myself “how does the knowledge offered in this book further our understanding of the WLF movement and social movements in general?”. In fact, many of the ideas of the progressive intellectuals examined in this book have inspired pro-democracy protesters, while those of conservative thinkers justify and support their repression. Kamrava does not elaborate on the connection between (what might look like) abstract intellectuality and material social processes, and neither does he reflect on how diffused political discontent coalesce into a social movement. However, we know that connection exists thanks to the very real exchanges that take place in the everyday life of ordinary people, like the participants to my research have often emphasised, in the form of critical intellectuals being university professors and, as such, conveying their ideas to students or “whisper networks” among high-school girls who share women’s magazines conveying feminist ideas built on progressive interpretations of Islamic jurisprudence.¹ The lack of

1 See Rivetti, P. (2020). *Political Participation in Iran from Khatami to the Green Movement*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.

a solid production in the social history of intellectual change in Iran— one which shows how the epistemic revolutions in the world of religious intellectuality relate to the “every-day stories” of ordinary people—is one of the reasons why we know little about how social movements and intellectual production interact. Along with strengthening knowledge in this field, scholars of the future also should foreground the work of women intellectuals, whose theoretical elaboration is clearly missing and overlooked in the scholarship about Iranian intellectuals.

Such blind spots hinder developments in another area: the analysis of liberatory and emancipatory religious and/or secular political thought; one that foregrounds anti-carceral, intersectional analyses that go beyond a liberal and procedural understanding of rights and democracy. Looking at the intellectual production of overlooked scholars who may sit at the margins of academia and “acceptable” intellectual networks, may reveal original theorisation about topics which are less spoken about, such as structural racism or inequality under neoliberal capitalism in Iran. The lack of radical and de-colonial analyses among progressive thinkers in Iran is something that social scientists of Iran are starting to notice. This is a fertile area for researchers because there is only little published work, as of yet. The influence of the Iranian state and its post-colonial posture is an important factor influencing and determining the liberal-looking attitude of Iranian thinkers who are critical of the Islamic Republic, and who struggle to engage topics such as racism or anti-capitalism, as they are weaponised in an anti-Western and anti-liberal function. These are layers of analysis that the scholars of contemporary Iran have yet to fully unpack. One possible venue for engagement in this type of investigation is diasporic

intellectual and political production. As a result of the repression of the WLF movement, many progressive activists and students have left Iran for destinations where Egyptian, Syrian, Tunisian, Sudanese, Libyan, Palestinian, Lebanese, Turkish, and Kurdish progressive activists, students, and thinkers already reside because of the repression they've endure in the past decades. How are diasporic encounters influencing the intellectual production of Iranian activists? And if there are no mutual influence and exchange, why is that? It is from such encounters that a “radical” transformation of progressive Iranian political thought might develop.

In conclusion, Kamrava's *How Islam Rules Iran* is a must-read for social scientists who are interested in a solid investigation of how religion and politics are imbricated in Iran, but also for those who are interested in imagining Iranian intellectuality and its relation to Islam beyond the state and the confines of justifying the existence of – or the need to reform – the Islamic Republic.

Eric Lob, Florida International University

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In his book *How Islam Rules Iran*, Mehran Kamrava presents a cogent and accessible account of state-religion relations and religious and intellectual trends and developments in the Islamic Republic of Iran before, during, and after the Iranian Revolution of 1979.

Kamrava bases his account on previously untapped, primary sources in Persian, that he collected inside and outside of Iran. By examining the Islamic Republic's ideological origins and dimensions, Kamrava supplements his recently published books on its consolidation and resilience from the realist and materialist perspective of structure, agency, power, and institutionalism (Kamrava 2022, 2023).

In his book and in a constructivist fashion, Kamrava traces the three phases of the Islamic Republic's ideological evolution and trajectory from the pre-revolutionary period to the present day. The first phase took place before and during the revolution, between the 1960s and early 1980s, when Ayatollah Ruhollah Khomeini (1979-89) and his circle of revolutionary clerics consolidated power. During this period, there existed an interpretative opening that included Khomeini's innovative and foundational concept of the "guardianship of the juriconsult" (*velayat-e faqih*). The latter deviated from the quietist tradition of Shiism by declaring that a supreme leader should rule over the state and community in accordance with Islamic law.

The second phase occurred during the reformist presidency of Mohammad Khatami (1997-2005) from the late 1990s to the early 2000s. These years constituted another hermeneutical opening among clerical and lay thinkers who contested the late Khomeini's central concept. Within an Islamic interpretative and intellectual framework, and as also described by Eskandar Sadeghi-Boroujerdi (2019) in his renowned book on the reformist movement, these thinkers challenged the religiopolitical status quo by (re-)introducing ideas involving authority, legitimacy, sovereignty, and democracy. Ultimately, they were censored and coerced by conservatives and hardliners led by Khomeini's successor, Ali Khamenei (1989-present). While being subjected to conservative repression and Western pressure, the reformists failed to convert their ideological constructs into tangible policies, causing societal disillusionment and political defeat.

Under Khamenei's leadership and after the Green Movement uprising of 2009, the third and final phase consisted of his political and ideological consolidation, which Kamrava calls "Khameneism." Compared with Khomeinism, as conceptualized by Ervand Abrahamian (1993) in his seminal book by the same title, Khameneism may lack the same level of Third World political populism that manifested itself in Iran's hardline president,

Mahmoud Ahmadinejad (2005-13). That said, Kamrava contends that it contains comparable degrees of conservatism, authoritarianism, paranoia, and intolerance. Kamrava concludes by contemplating the Islamic Republic's future and questioning whether Khameneism will outlive its maker, as the supreme leader grows older and as the succession issue looms large. Despite the Islamic Republic's disdain for the dynastic succession of its monarchical predecessor, and the inexistence of such a practice in the Shia clerical establishment, it would not be unexpected if Khameneism endured due to the institutionalization of the supreme leader's position and office – a process and outcome that Kamrava highlights in this book and his previous one on Iran (2023).

Broadening the analytical lens beyond Iran's idiosyncratic brand of Shia theology and jurisprudence, alongside its unique blend of religion and republicanism, which Kamrava details in his book, the Islamic Republic is indeed *sui generis* by possessing clerical leadership. At the same time, it remains unexceptional from a religious and revolutionary standpoint. Religiously, the Islamic Republic is both a cause and consequence of Muslim religious scholars (*ulama*) increasingly perceiving themselves as custodians and practicing religiopolitical activism while being bureaucratized by some states. In his book, Muhammad Qasim Zaman (2007) deftly documents this discursive development and contemporary change not only in Iran, but also in Pakistan, Egypt, Saudi Arabia, India, and the Philippines.

Like its revolutionary counterparts in China and Russia, the Islamic Republic exhibits weak civil-military relations and oligarchic tendencies. Additionally, the Islamic Republic's

political trajectory has contained the consolidation of both supreme leaders, interspersed with intermittent reformism during the presidencies of Khatami and, to a lesser extent, Hassan Rouhani (2013-21), and potentially Masoud Pezeshkian (2024-present). After the death of China's revolutionary leader Mao Zedong (1949-76) in 1978, political elites from within the Chinese Communist Party began undertaking economic reforms to transition the republic from state socialism to market capitalism. In the end, they were repressed by party hardliners before such reforms could encompass democratization and liberalization, culminating in the crackdown on the Tiananmen Square protests in 1989. Following decades of authoritarian rule and economic centralization in the wake of the Russian Revolution, Mikhail Gorbachev (1985-91) and Boris Yeltsin (1991-99) implemented sweeping political and economic reforms before and after the fall of the Soviet Union during the 1980s and 1990s. The political turmoil and economic adversity that accompanied these reforms set the stage for the rise and consolidation of Vladimir Putin (2000-08, 2012-present) starting in 2000 until today.

To conclude, Kamrava's book permits students and specialists of Iran and Shiism to process the ideological pillars and phases of the Islamic Republic's religiopolitical consolidation and contestation – from Khomeini's revolutionary regime to Khatami's reformist renaissance to Khamenei's reactionary repression. It also pushes scholars of area and religious studies to ponder how these pillars and phases possess parallels with the perceptions and practices of *ulama* in other parts of the Middle East and Muslim world. Finally, the book compels comparativists to contemplate the commonalities concerning the evolutionary trajectory of the Islamic Republic and

other revolutionary states.

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Norma Clair Moruzzi, University of Illinois

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Mehran Kamrava's *How Islam Rules in Iran* is an erudite and accessible work of scholarship. Whether sought out as a refresher for the details of specific theological and jurisprudential arguments, or for an overview of the evolution of a national political-religious discourse, the book is accurate and readable, making a valuable contribution to the literature on the Islamic Republic both for specialists and those less familiar with arguments within the discourse of Iranian political Islam. It is clearly written and admirably jargon free, and the notes are helpfully included at the bottom of the page (thank you, Cambridge University Press). However, the project is not reflected in the title. This is not a book about how Islam rules Iran; it is a book of intellectual history and the theological and political arguments within the state's clerical elite.

The details of this elite intellectual infighting can be fascinating. Kamrava traces the political implications of theological squabbles over justifications for clerical leadership or moral authority. Following the internal fissures within the Iranian religious (primarily clerical) elite over the proper role of Islam—and their role as its designated interpreters—within the Islamic Republic, Kamrava reveals the trend toward increasing orthodoxy (both

religious and political) within the clerical-political leadership. The ideological turn towards rigid conservatism is reflected in the increasing consolidation of institutional control within a narrow circle of cadres whose chief merit has been their fealty to the elderly Supreme Leader, Ali Khamenei. Kamrava tracks this intertwined intellectual and political trend, manifested through jurisprudential argument, from the intellectual precursors of the revolution, including but not limited to Khomeini himself, through to the almost-current national situation, relating the subtle differences and evolving positions among both well-known and relatively under-studied contributors to an ongoing debate. Kamrava terms the resulting ideology and institutional politics to be *Khameneism*, and he argues that it has become hegemonic.

All scholars worry that a completed research project will be unexpectedly overtaken by events. This book seems to have been completed after the 2022 death of Mahsa Jina Amini and the ensuing protests of the Iranian Women, Life, Freedom movement. Kamrava's short final chapter recognizes that the consolidation of conservative clerical institutional authority the book chronicles has not been accepted by large swaths of Iranian society, and that regime stability is challenged by

unaddressed problems of gender inequality and the recurrent threat of widespread popular unrest. The chapter sits uneasily with the overall argument that *Khameneism* has become Iran's successfully dominant mode of state governance and that postrevolutionary republicanism is essentially dead. But it seems to have been written before the surprise political events of the spring and summer 2024. In May, hardline President Ebrahim Raisi was killed in a helicopter crash. Reformist-affiliated candidate Masoud Pezeshkian, who received permission to stand as a candidate in the resulting June Presidential election, did well enough to qualify for the July run-off election, and won. The shock was not so much that the Pezeshkian could win, but that he was allowed to win. Kamrava rightly notes that the period from the contested 2009 election of President Mahmoud Ahmadinejad through the Raisi Presidency revealed a continuous and apparently successful institutional effort, both intellectual and political, to control elections and consolidate an authoritarian and exclusionary model of governance based on the most absolutist versions of *velayat-e faqih* (rule by the supreme jurist), initiated by Ayatollah Ruhollah Khomeini, and developed as a justified institutional practice by Supreme Leader Khamenei. But Pezeshkian's permitted candidacy and acknowledged electoral victory illustrate one of the Islamic Republic's other chief characteristics: its adaptability. It is quite possible that the 2009-2023 period of *Khameneism's* intellectual and institutional hegemony has come to an end.

How Islam Rules in Iran is a thorough consideration of Iranian theocratic discourse, including the frequent hostility within that discourse to the actively republican elements of the dual state. But I would argue that methodologies that confine the study

of politics to only formal institutions and discourses risk missing underlying social tensions and popular discontents, especially when examining authoritarian systems. States exist in relation with their societies. In Iran, the push-pull of state and society relations has consistently resulted in the secularization and liberalization of a society more and more distanced from the state's Islamic ideology and religious governing structures. This has happened even as state ideologues have attempted to assert themselves by appropriating institutional control to a narrow base of the most orthodox. Yet the theocratic leadership's unexpected decision to permit a more open election, and to recalibrate the uneasy balance of Islamic and republican state elements, indicates an admission that the recent period's institutional bet on consolidated *Khameneism* has failed. The state has adapted, and it appears we are re-entering an era of internal state-society negotiation rather than overt and constant confrontation. Despite the extremities of its orthodox public discourse, the Islamic Republic remains a complex and dynamic dual entity, challenging us to apply equivalently complex and adaptable research methodologies.

Response by Mehran Kamrava, Georgetown University, Qatar

Mehran Kamrava is Professor of Government at Georgetown University in Qatar. He also directs the Iranian Studies Unit at the Arab Center for Research and Policy Studies. Kamrava is the author of a number of journal articles and books, including, most recently, How Islam Rules in Iran: Theology and Theocracy in the Islamic Republic (Cambridge University Press, 2024); Righteous Politics: Power and Resilience in Iran (Cambridge University Press, 2023); A Dynastic History of Iran: From the Qajars to the Pahlavis (Cambridge University Press, 2022); Triumph and Despair: In Search of Iran's Islamic Republic (Oxford University Press, 2022); A Concise History of Revolution (Cambridge University Press, 2020); Troubled Waters: Insecurity in the Persian Gulf (Cornell University Press, 2018); Inside the Arab State (Oxford University Press, 2018); The Impossibility of Palestine: History, Geography, and the Road Ahead (Yale University Press, 2016).

All authors like to see their works reviewed, and it is especially gratifying when the reviewers are gifted scholars. I am grateful to Eric Lob, Norma Claire Moruzzi, and Paola Rivetti for their gracious reviews. I owe special thanks for Gamze Cavdar for having arranged the book roundtable on *How Islam Rules in Iran*.

All three reviews largely agree with the central arguments of the books, and therefore there is not much in terms of substantive analysis for me to address. I will therefore confine my comments here to three main themes highlighted by the reviewers. The first has to do with the question of women, who, as Rivetti rightly points out, have been largely left out of the intellectual discourse in Iran. I address this “blind spot” on page 237.

This neglect of gender issues has been a chronic feature of the intellectual production of Iran's religious intellectuals both on the right and the left of the ideological spectrum. Especially striking has been the inability, or cultural and political unwillingness, of so-called religious “new thinkers,” both in the

mid- to the late 1990s and in more recent years, to make women's issues part of their intellectual discourse.¹

Related to the issue of women is the social movement that erupted in Iran in the aftermath of the killing of a 22-year-old woman, Mahsa Amini, at the hands of the state's morality police. Both Rivetti and Moruzzi wish the book delved deeper into the connection between prevailing intellectual currents and unfolding social processes. While acknowledging the validity of their arguments, in *How Islam Rules in Iran* I mention, perhaps insufficiently, how the intellectuals' unwillingness to tackle women's issues fostered the social movement of 2022:

By late 2022, Iranians of all walks of life, especially the young and particularly young women, took matters into their own hands, removed their compulsory hijabs en masse, shouted slogans about women's freedom, and refused to eat in segregated university cafeterias. As the Islamic Republic entered its fourth decade, young Iranian women and men demonstrated with their

1 Mehran Kamrava, *Iran's Intellectual Revolution*. (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2008), p. 22.

deeds what their father's generation had pretended to care for but had failed to theorize about (p. 302).

I have elaborated on the outbreak of the Mahsa Amini movement and women's larger treatment by the Islamic Republic elsewhere.²

The core arguments of the book are geared toward analyzing “the ways in which current religious intellectual production in Iran has shaped evolving political–religious discourses in the country, impacted the ongoing transformation of Iranian Shi‘ism, and has ultimately underwritten the political survival and fate of the Islamic Republic” (vii-viii). To this end, I have devoted some significant space to “Khameneism” (chapter 8), a notion inspired by Ervand Abrahamian's perceptive “Khomeinism.” Given the post-publication election of the reformist Masoud Pezeshkian as president, Moruzzi maintains that “the chapter sits uneasily with the overall argument that *Khameneism* has become Iran's successfully dominant mode of state governance, and that postrevolutionary republicanism is essentially dead.” The state's inherent adaptability, she argues, demonstrates that “consolidated *Khameneism* has failed.”

Built-in adaptability is indeed a source of resilience for the Islamic Republic, a phenomenon I have explored extensively elsewhere.³ But adaptability as manifested in the reformists' presidential victory hardly amounts to a negation of Khameneism as I have outlined in the book. In my conceptualization, as the book amply demonstrates, Khameneism constitutes first and foremost the practical manifestation of an important ideological innovation within Shia thought, one that

2 Mehran Kamrava, “Women, Life, Liberty: Protesting the Islamic Republic,” *Case Analysis, Arab Center for Research and Policy Studies*, (October 4, 2022), pp. 1-4; Mehran Kamrava, “From Misogyny to Security: Women and the State in Iran,” *Third World Quarterly*, forthcoming.

3 Mehran Kamrava, *Righteous Politics: Power and Resilience in Iran*, (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2023), pp. 226-299.

goes beyond specific political developments. An entire group of state ideologists, many of them with clerical backgrounds and based in Qom and elsewhere, busy themselves with articulating the ideological minutia of a theology centered around the person of Khomeini. The main focus of these rightist religious scholars is to provide theoretical justifications for Khomeini's practice of clerical absolutism, a theoretical innovation within Shia jurisprudence first politically articulated by Khomeini. Khomeini has put into full practice a notion that Khomeini introduced close to the end of his life.

The resulting ideological corpus deals primarily with two questions: 1) the origins of political legitimacy – divine versus popular, as examined in the book's chapter 7; and, 2) the scope of the *Velayat-e Faqih's* authority – absolute versus limited and conditional, as discussed in chapter 8. As Lob rightly observes, I do wonder whether Khameneism will outlive Khomeini; most likely it will not. For now, however, it remains fully in force.

The fact that the reformist president saw it prudent to run his cabinet nominees by Khomeini *before* formally presenting them to the Majles speaks volumes as to the scope of the Leader's authority. For the time being, Khameneism continues to undergird the theological foundations of the Islamic Republic as the system (*nezam*) has taken shape in the post-Khomeini era.

From authors' perspective, “good” reviews are those that make a work ultimately stronger. As such, I am grateful to all three reviewers for helping me with their excellent reviews.♦